

Does playing a musical instrument prevent and reduce the onset of cognitive decline in old aged individuals?

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ABSTRACT

Objectives: Specific levels of mentally stimulating activity are hypothesised to mitigate against cognitive impairment in older individuals. Musical instruments playing, whether in a band or individually can be a viable source of such mental stimulation. To date, more than 50 journals have featured such articles regarding the study of musical mental stimulation on reducing cognitive decline.

Methods: Systematic review and analysis of any study with musical instruments and musical mental stimulation with effects on cognitive decline and impairment over a period of time in old aged individuals.

Results: 15 unduplicated and non-identical studies were reviewed and identified from literature searches through Scopus, ScienceDirect and PubMed, four of which were included and reported. Two twin studies and two on cohort studies. All studies were of good methodological quality and reported large effects of musical instrument implementation in the reduction or prevention of cognitive decline, such as impairment or dementia

Conclusion: The six studies analysed show decreased risk of developing cognition impairment or decline with the exposure to music therapy (active, passive and composition)

Introduction

As global populations continue to age, understanding causes and mitigating factors which influence cognitive decline has become an urgent priority. Conditions such as dementia, and Alzheimer's disease significantly impact the quality of life for older aged individuals, and for their care systems. Current research into prevention strategies often lacks focus on specific lifestyle factors. Whilst mental stimulation is often cited as a protective factor, much of the existing literature published has concentrated on physical activity, such as sports, running and triathlon, as well as visual arts and other forms of engagement. In contrast, such musical stimulation, particularly the act of playing a musical instrument, has received little attention despite the cognitive demand and widespread popularity amongst younger individuals. Musical engagement involves complex interactions between auditory processing, motor movement and coordination, and memory, making it a powerful tool and method of stimulation for maintaining positive cognitive health.

Methods

The data on the long-term cognitive consequences of musical practice in older populations is noticeably lacking, however. Research on this topic remains limited, especially during the search period. This review was collated with literature searches on Scopus, ScienceDirect, PubMed, SciSpace and OpenScienceFramework, within the dates of 02 May 2025 and 11 May 2025 using the search terms: (Music OR Practice OR Musical Practice or Musical OR Mental Stimulation) AND (Cognitive Decline OR Cognitive OR Dementia OR Maintain OR Effect) AND (Memory OR Recall OR Cogni_). Google Scholar was not used due to technical issues in the period of 02 May 2025 and 11 May 2025. All collected data has been sorted and collated into appropriate sections. Only peer-reviewed studies reporting cognitive outcomes to musical engagement in older adults (over 50 years) were included and within a publication period of 10 years (2015-2025). Each article was screened for relevance based on titles, abstracts and the full texts. Studies that focused on unrelated

FIGURE 1: Methodology flowchart

forms of mental stimulation such as the aforementioned physical activity, or visual arts have been omitted to ensure clarity and focus. Data from the six selected studies were organised and grouped by study design, and type of musical intervention. To ensure reliability, only studies reporting data with a minimum 95% confidence interval were considered as part of this paper which were either inferred or explicitly outlined in each publication. Hazard ratios were extracted directly from original publications and cited directly. Additional calculations were carried out with basic statistical tools such as "Calculator" and open-access simulations provided by academic institutions such as Cox Regression.

Results

The initial findings from this review support the hypothesis in which leisure activities may have protective effects against specific impairment in cognition, however the specific links between musical stimulation and the reduced risks of such cognitive decline remain obscure and is not well established as of recent. According to multiple works published recently, the most consistent and assessed strategies for slowing or preventing cognitive decline include abstaining from alcohol and tobacco, as well as maintaining regular physical activity (Kennedy et al., 2016). While playing a musical instrument is a popular activity known to support mental wellbeing and cognitive function, the direct impact between incidence of cognitive is still inconclusive and actively being researched (Dingle et al., 2021; Wesseldijk et al., 2019). A review of data from BMC Neurology highlighted the inadequacy of high-quality and peer

reviewed studies focused on the engagement in music and potential protective factors. In the synthesis of three key studies, referred to as the 'Bronx', 'MoVIES' and 'JAGES' studies, sample sizes and demographic distribution varied significantly, as partially shown in Figure 2. For example, both the 'Bronx' and 'MoVIES' studies were conducted in the United States and based on older participants (minimum 65-75 years), however has limited gender balance, and with female participants representing 64% and 66.5% of the sample respectively. In contrast however, the 'JAGES' study consisted of a demographically diverse Japanese sample, where more than 52,000 individuals were included, from over 31 distinct regions of the country. The female representation in this study was more balanced, at 53.9%. Median follow-up periods ranged from 5.1 years (Bronx), to 5.9 years ('MoVIES' and 'JAGES' combined average), suggesting that longer durations of observations may improve the strength of outcomes in results. Hazard ratios were used across studies to assess the risk reduction value. In the BMC Neurology publication, consisting of the three aforementioned studies, the average hazard ratio for individuals engaged in music was below 1.0, with a 95% confidence interval, indicating a lower chance of cognitive decline in musically active participants. In article 2, published in the 'International Journal of Alzheimer's Disease', which utilised a twin study design, reported a hazard ratio of 0.68, with little difference from article 1, outlining a further potential benefit. According to Brody (2012), a hazard ratio below 1.0 suggests that the treatment group (for example here, musically active individuals) has a reduced risk in developing the outcome in question, compared to the control group. In a third study analysing monozygotic (identical) twins, one was musically active, and the other was not, 59.3% of non-musician twins showed dementia, while 40.7% exhibited other forms of cognitive decline or impairment. In contrast, all musically engaged twins remained cognitively intact with a 0% studied value of cognitive decline or impairment such as Alzheimer's or dementia. These findings from the third entry outline a strong suggestion of protective association between musical practice and cognitive health. Most importantly, all studies have adjusted their results for confounding variables such as age, sex, education level and other lifestyle factors. While causation can not yet be confirmed, the consistency of results between multiple cohort and twins studies from different demographic regions strengthens the argument that musical engagement may perform a beneficial role in delaying, or reducing the onset of cognitive

Study	Participants	Country	Minimum Age	% Women	Follow-Up period (years)	Incidence of dementia (%)
Bronx	469	US 1	75	64	5.1 median	26.4
MoVIES	943	US 1	65	66.5	6.1 median	11.8
JAGES	52601	JA 81	65	53.9	5.8 median	11.0

FIGURE 2: Results of study from Literature Review (BMC Neurology)

decline in old aged individuals and aging populations. In a fourth study, Vetere et al. (2024), an analysis of data from a sample of 1,000 adults aged 40 and above, it was found that individuals who played musical instruments exhibited significantly better memory and executive cognitive function. Singing was also associated with such improved function. These findings further emphasizes the potential cognitive benefits of musical engagement in older individuals. Building on this Rogers & Metzler-Baddeley (2024), investigated how musical engagement and training affected older individual's working memory and fluid intelligence. They discovered that, in comparison to control groups, participants who received treatment of a 10-week training period significantly improved their awareness and cognitive-related tasks. These findings also point to the possibility that musical training may be a useful strategy for delaying or preventing the onset of cognitive aging by improving cognitive abilities that normally deteriorate with age.

In their 2025 publication in *The Gerontologist*, Zhou et al. conducted a comprehensive review and analysis examine the effects of music therapy on cognitive functioning in older individuals. With results from 33 randomised controlled trials with a total sample of 3,058 participants, the study presents a robust and grounded evaluation of music's role in cognitive aging to date. The primary aim of such study was to determine whether musical interventions, broadly listed as active; singing or instrument playing, and passive; listening which can significantly enhance specific factors of cognition such as memory, function and total performance. Key findings demonstrated that music led to a significant statistical improvement across all three domains as aforementioned;

- Global cognition, improved with mean difference (MD) of 0.40, suggesting a positive effect.
- Memory, improved with a MD of 0.25, and,
- Executive function, improved with a MD of 0.37.

All three factors were measured with a 95% confidence interval to ensure reliability of data.

By demonstrating consistent results, the authors and researchers provide compelling research and evidence for incorporating music as an intervention for cognitive aging. Importantly, the study also groups sub-studies based on the type of intervention, active music therapy (such as playing an instrument or singing) showed stronger effects than passive listening, providing additional support for the idea that active engagement may yield stronger effects. Such interventions that were also adapted to each demographic's cultural or relevancy to their sample demonstrated higher effectiveness, suggesting the need to adapt programs to ensure maximum benefits with little to no harm as a form of beneficence.

To compare collected values, see

Discussion

The findings presented in this review suggest a still emerging, but promising relationship between musical engagement and the reduction of cognitive decline in older aged individuals. While traditional interventions such as physical activity and diet regulations have been established as effective in slowing the onset of cognitive impairment, musical stimulation presents itself as contemporary research topic which is potentially impactful for further exploration. The reviewed cohort and twin studies demonstrated that individuals who participate in musical activities regularly, such as playing an instrument, may exhibit a lower risk of developing dementia or other forms of cognitive impairment. The cognitive demands evidently involved in musical practice may help explain its potentially protective effects especially as it demands movement in memory, motor coordination and movement, auditory processing and emotional regulation. These activities engage simultaneously, further enhancing any researched effects especially the plasticity of the brain and reduction in aging (Rajakumar & Mohan, 2024). However, limitations in current research to date must be fully acknowledged, many studies had small sample sizes, or demographically indifferent samples, or potentially short follow-up periods, at only 6.88% of the average life-span of

individuals (subject to differences depending on demographic region). In addition, causality can not be confirmed as many individuals with a higher cognitive functioning are more likely to pursue such musical hobbies where data will be skewed. While hazard ratios across all analysed studies suggest a benefit to musical stimulation, more rigorous and advanced research is needed to define causal links. In the future, studies should aim to include larger and more diverse samples and control for more confounding factors, as well as type of involvement as to determine whether specific reductions are specific to each type of involvement or not.

To conclude, while basic evidence supports the idea that musical engagement may contribute to the reduced risk of cognitive decline, the field remains undeveloped and expanding research in such area will not only gather valuable insights into cognitive health, but also promote enriching strategies for aging well as individuals.

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References

- [01] 4. *Statements of probability and confidence intervals*. (n.d.). The Bmj. Retrieved May 10, 2025, from <https://www.bmj.com/about-bmj/resources-readers/publications/statistics-square-one/4-statements-probability-and-confidence>
- [02] Arafa, A., Teramoto, M., Maeda, S., Sakai, Y., Nosaka, S., Gao, Q., Kawachi, H., Kashima, R., Matsumoto, C., & Kokubo, Y. (2022). Playing a musical instrument and the risk of dementia among older adults: a systematic review and meta-analysis of prospective cohort studies. *BMC Neurology*, 22(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12883-022-02902-z>
- [03] Balbag, M. A., Pedersen, N. L., & Gatz, M. (2014). Playing a Musical Instrument as a Protective Factor against Dementia and Cognitive Impairment: A Population-Based Twin Study. *International Journal of Alzheimer S Disease*, 2014, 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2014/836748>
- [04] Brody, T. (2012). 9. Biostatistics. In *Clinical Trials* (pp. 169–170). <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-391911-3.00009-8>
- [05] Chait, M., White, S., Thomas, C., Vranes, N., Velardo, G., Condon, E., Rozario, J., Ellul, J., Marshall, D., Goold, B., & Curtis, L. (2023). *Edrolo VCE Psychology Units 1&2* (2nd ed.). Edrolo.
- [06] Grame, C, T., Westrup, & Allan, J. (2025, March 17). *Musical instrument | History, Characteristics, Examples, & Facts*. Encyclopedia Britannica. <https://www.britannica.com/art/musical-instrument>
- [07] Guo, S., Feng, L., Chen, J., Li, Y., Bian, H., Li, L., Yang, H., Lu, J., & Yao, D. (2023). The effect of music intervention on cognitive aging: from the view of EEG microstates. *Research Square (Research Square)*. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2868131/v1>
- [08] Hanna-Pladdy, B., & MacKay, A. (2011). The relation between instrumental musical activity and cognitive aging. *Neuropsychology*, 25(3), 378–386. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0021895>
- [09] Raglio, A., & Attardo, L. (2020). Music therapy in dementia: The effects of music therapy and other musical interventions on behavior, emotion, and cognition. In *Diagnosis and Management in Dementia* (Vol. 1, pp. 695–711). <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-12-815854-8.00044-6>
- [10] Rajakumar, K. D., & Mohan, J. (2024). A systematic review on effect of music intervention on cognitive impairment using EEG, fMRI, and cognitive assessment modalities. *Results in Engineering*, 22, 102224. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rineng.2024.102224>
- [11] Rogers, F., & Metzler-Baddeley, C. (2024). The effects of musical instrument training on fluid intelligence and executive functions in healthy older adults: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Brain and Cognition*, 175, 106137. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bandc.2024.106137>
- [12] Seinfeld, S., Figueroa, H., Ortiz-Gil, J., & Sanchez-Vives, M. V. (2013). Effects of music learning and piano practice on cognitive function, mood and quality of life in older adults. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 4. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2013.00810>
- [13] Vetere, G., Williams, G., Ballard, C., Creese, B., Hampshire, A., Palmer, A., Pickering, E., Richards, M., Brooker, H., & Corbett, A. (2024). The relationship between playing musical instruments and cognitive trajectories: Analysis from a UK ageing cohort. *International Journal*

of Geriatric Psychiatry, 39(2). <https://doi.org/10.1002/gps.6061>

[14] Vincenzi, M., Borella, E., Sella, E., Lima, C. F., De Beni, R., & Schellenberg, E. G. (2022). Music listening, emotion, and cognition in older adults. *Brain Sciences*, 12(11), 1567. <https://doi.org/10.3390/brainsci12111567>

[15] Walsh, S., Causer, R., & Brayne, C. (2019). Does playing a musical instrument reduce the incidence of cognitive impairment and dementia? A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Aging & Mental Health*, 25(4), 593–601. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13607863.2019.1699019>

[16] Wirth, M., Böttcher, A., Höppner, A., Fabel, K., Köbe, T., Teipel, S. J., Peters, O., Priller, J., Schneider, A., Wiltfang, J., Buerger, K., Perneczky, R., Laske, C., Spottke, A., Jessen, F., Düzel, E., Wagner, M., & Roeske, S. (2021). Lifelong music practice as reserve factor: Associations with cognition and brain structure in older adults. *Alzheimer S & Dementia*, 17(S10). <https://doi.org/10.1002/alz.055411>

[17] Zhou, M., Wei, C., Xie, X., Wang, Z., Chen, L., & Zhang, X. (2025). Effect of music therapy on cognitive function among older adults: A systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *The Gerontologist*. <https://doi.org/10.1093/geront/gnaf106>